

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL-METHODICAL TRAINING OF TEACHERS IN CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The article deals with the problems of the improvement of professional and methodic preparedness of the teachers.*

Keywords: *continuous professional development, educational institutions, professional-methodical training of pedagogues, basic competencies, information and communication technologies, professional qualifications, new knowledge, competencies, international experiences, educational needs, professional activity, research results and analyses.*

As our republic aims to build a democratic society as an independent country and become one of the most developed countries in the world, it also sets certain tasks for the system of continuous professional development of preschool and school education workers. These tasks are determined by the development of professional and methodical training of pedagogues working in educational institutions. Professional-methodical training of teachers is reflected in their main areas of professional activity, such as professional knowledge, organization of the educational process, and self-development. This, in turn, requires the pedagogue to perfectly know and apply the knowledge related to the teaching of his subject, acquire the basic competencies necessary for designing, organizing and evaluating the educational process, as well as the teaching and upbringing process. requires intensive organization, continuous and systematic self-development based on innovative scientific achievements in the field of education, modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies.

Positive changes in the professional activity and personal qualities of the pedagogue, who has enriched and deepened his professional qualification with new knowledge, the acquisition of the educational competencies specified in the state educational standards of the students, ultimately the increase in the quality and efficiency of education, education is a pedagogical guarantee of the successful operation of the institution. Based on this, in the era of globalization, it is necessary to organize and liberalize the process of continuous professional development based on the needs of the times, to freely choose the forms and terms of independent education, to prioritize the professional-methodical training of pedagogues on the basis of national harmony and international experiences.

The system of continuous professional development, organized and liberalized on the basis of the educational needs of pedagogues, aimed at continuous and independent professional development, clarified the activity of the teacher, encouraged him to solve the unresolved practical tasks of education and training, and optimally organized the educational process. prepares the ground. Self-development of the pedagogue through continuous and independent professional development - the pedagogue organizes practical actions on the basis of clear goals and well-thought-out tasks in order to improve professional experience, qualifications and skills, having a

deep understanding of his mission. development of professional competence, formation of necessary competences in students, comprehensive development of him as a person and acquisition of knowledge on organization of educational process is ensured. Based on the above, below we will describe in detail the development of professional and methodical training of pedagogues in the continuous professional development system.

Methodical training is the main final phase of professional training. It is the acquisition of methodical knowledge that creates the professional training of a pedagogue. Professional-methodical training of educators is determined by their possession of the following methodological knowledge: knowledge of the peculiarities of teaching technologies and the organization of various types of teaching, the ability to appropriately use the pedagogue's means of communicative influence on the audience, collective thinking being able to organize and so on.

We studied some aspects of scientific research on this problem in order to gain a fundamental understanding of the development of professional and methodical training of educators.

V.V. Latyushin's article entitled "Anthropologically-centered approach to professional-pedagogical training of a future teacher" shows four main stages of professional development of a person in higher education institutions: content, dynamic (after entering a higher education institution independent expression of a person's conscious professional creativity); institutional (environment of professional development of a person) and technological (management tools, methods and forms, situations of anthropological focus in professional training).

D.O.Khimmataliyev "considers preparation for professional activity to be the result of special training and development of professional knowledge, skills, basic mental tasks, professional orientation of education, upbringing and self-education, professional self-determination includes a set", - states [2; p. 104]. Also, the author divides the requirements that ensure the readiness of a modern pedagogue for professional activity in research work into the following two groups: invariant intellectual skills of social, professional and personal importance that ensure the teacher's readiness to solve basic problems at various levels, and the formation of individual qualities, as well as , requirements for the content of fundamental knowledge and the level of their formation, which serve to ensure the teacher's readiness to solve basic problems at different levels [2; 38-b.].

I. Y. Rakhmonov said that "methodical training of a teacher is the educational process and its result, in which teaching can be carried out for the purpose of educating a person (generally or in some field of knowledge) or for the purpose of acquiring a certain professional specialty." emphasizes [1; p. 38]. Achieving the first goal primarily involves the formation of a certain knowledge system and personal characteristics, while the second goal is often achieved through the formation of skills and qualifications necessary for professional activity.

Above [1; 2] in the scientific-research work, although the future teacher's preparation for professional activity and professional development issues were researched in higher education institutions, the ideas and results obtained during the scientific-research work in the system of continuous professional development of the pedagogue can be used in the development of methodological preparation components and its basic requirements.

As a result of the results of scientific research and analysis, as well as our observations, we came to the conclusion that in the process of continuous professional development, it is necessary

to take into account the development of the following components of professional and methodical training of pedagogues:

- development of managerial and technological methods and techniques in pedagogical activity;
- design, organization and implementation of each specific type of pedagogical activity;
- design and implementation of pedagogical technologies logically completed in the teaching process;
- taking into account the educational needs and level of knowledge of learners when promoting pedagogical issues;
- evaluating and taking into account the results of the students' activities;
- development of learner's motivation;
- formation of mutual relations with the learner during the educational process;
- to be able to see the educational needs of learners and the demands of society;
- defining the perspective of formation of professional competence and its implementation;
- creating a methodical system for the learner to learn effectively and achieve results;
- creation and implementation of a methodical system of training students for international assessment studies.

The above comments, the analysis of scientific research and the current state of the continuous professional development system showed the feasibility of forming a continuous professional development process aimed at developing the professional and methodical training of educators, taking into account the professional needs of pedagogues, based on the following requirements:

- that in the process of continuous professional development, the independent search for knowledge and their assimilation is provided by learners;
- organization of the process of continuous professional development in accordance with the latest achievements of science, technology, and technology, as well as compliance with the requirements of ensuring coherence and continuity in the public education system.

The conclusion is that in the educational process, the content of education, teaching, and learning are so closely related that none of them can be ignored. Both teaching and learning depend on the object of education directed to the main goal and the final result - the content of education, which depends on the teacher who organizes the learning. Therefore, in our opinion, the training of highly qualified pedagogic personnel and the development of their professional and methodical training should become a necessary condition for the development of society.

REFERENCES

1. Raxmonov I.Y. Geometriyani o'qitish jarayonida talabalarning metodik tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi: ped.f.nom.ilmij darajasini olish uchun yozilgan diss. – T.: 2012, –160 b.
2. Ximmataliyev D.O. Kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorgarlikni diagnostika qilishda pedagogik va texnik bilimlar integratsiyasi (texnika oliy ta'lim muassasalari "Kasb ta'limi" yo'nalishlari misolida): ped.f.dok.ilmij darajasini olish uchun yozilgan diss. – T.: 2012. –220 b.
3. Қодиров У.Д. Талаба-ёшларнинг мустақил таълим олиш фаолиятини ташкил этиш технологияси. "Талаба-ёшларни мустақил таълим олишга йўналтиришнинг педагогик-

психологик хусусиятлари” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари, 2023 йил 27 май.

4. Қодиров У.Д. Таҳдидбардош жамият тараққиётини таъминлашда шахс онгини шакллантириш масалалари. “Аниқ ва табиий фанларни ўқитишда замонавий ёндашув: муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари, 2023 йил 30 май.